

8T – Nature as a Set of Morphisms

O Manor

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Abstract:

By analyzing the ideas, main equations and methods of the 8T framework and using functors to vary to a setting of a set, analysis of nature can be presented in new and simpler manner as a set of arrows between objects.

Introduction

The first main equation, the variational manifold that validate Einstein principle of equivalence.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_1} \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial S_n} \frac{\partial S_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The second main equation, the primorial coupling constants series that proved bosons to be net curvature of discrete amounts on the matrix tensor.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2.1)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (2.11)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); \quad V \geq 0 \quad (2.12)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \quad \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); \quad P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (2.13)$$

Now we can define a functor to switch the setting, from a topological setting to a setting of a set. By doing so we can analyze nature in a completely different, hopefully simpler way.

$$\Lambda: Top \rightarrow Set$$

Now, we have a set with two elements as presented in equation (3):

$$K = (M, g) \tag{3}$$

The set has certain subsets. The first subset is the subset of primes or the number one. The manifold, or the set K, is generating the subset P. this subset is responsible for fermions clustering and bosonic propagations.

$$P = (2n + 1 \cup (+1)); \quad P \in K \tag{3.1}$$

The second subset is of even amount of curvature, which vanish into matter by threefold combination of two distinct elements that differ in sign. That is the subset described in the 8T by the arbitrary variation term presented in equation (3.2).

$$E = (2n); \quad E \in K \tag{3.2}$$

Finally, there is a morphism, isomorphism in particular given by the same equation that validate Einstein principle of equivalence.

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \equiv \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \in K \tag{3.3}$$

The set will generate time invariant acceleration from subsets of the matrix tensor that has extremum amounts of curvature that stay as they are over time. Changing the setting of nature into a set category and then partitioning the set makes things, as the author believes easier to grasp.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)